

Secure and Resilient IoMT Node Deployment: Enhancing Privacy and Threat Mitigation with 3D Voronoi Diagrams and a PSO-GA Hybrid Algorithm in Healthcare Networks

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Abstract—The Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) is transforming healthcare by enabling real-time monitoring, diagnostics, and secure data-driven decision-making. However, IoMT networks are vulnerable to adversarial attacks, data breaches, and privacy threats, making secure and optimized node deployment a critical challenge. This paper presents a novel framework integrating 3D Voronoi diagrams and K-means clustering with a hybrid Particle Swarm Optimization-Genetic Algorithm (PSO-GA) to optimize IoMT node placement while enhancing security and resilience. Initially, K-means clustering distributes nodes, followed by spatial partitioning with 3D Voronoi diagrams. The PSO-GA hybrid algorithm then iteratively refines node positions, balancing rapid convergence with global exploration to achieve optimal configurations that improve coverage, energy efficiency, and secure data exchange. Additionally, the proposed approach integrates risk assessment techniques and privacy-preserving mechanisms to mitigate adversarial threats, ensuring robustness against poisoning and evasion attacks. By dynamically adapting to changing healthcare environments, the framework enhances network resiliency while aligning with AI security and privacy-by-design principles. Experimental results validate the algorithm's scalability and effectiveness, making it a promising solution for real-world IoMT applications in secure medical monitoring, diagnostics, and AI-driven threat intelligence.

Index Terms—Internet of Medical Things (IoMT), Node Deployment Optimization, 3D Voronoi Diagrams, Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Genetic Algorithm (GA), Energy Efficiency in Healthcare Networks, Privacy Preservation, Threat Mitigation

I. INTRODUCTION

As healthcare systems advance, strategically deploying Internet of Medical Things (IoMT) nodes is crucial for achieving reliable coverage, energy efficiency, and seamless data exchange across varied environments, from large hospitals to remote clinics [1]. These settings require smart placement strategies to manage spatial coverage and power consumption effectively [2]. Traditional 2D approaches often fail to address the complexities of 3D healthcare spaces, where patient mobility, ongoing procedures, and changing conditions demand real-time network adaptability [3].

To meet these challenges, advanced algorithms are essential for optimizing coverage, minimizing energy use, and ensuring network stability [4]. In addition, rising cybersecurity threats targeting healthcare systems call for integrated security measures. This work aligns with the European Cybersecurity Competence Centre (ECCC) objectives, embedding threat mitigation and privacy-preserving mechanisms into the design to protect against IoT-specific attacks such as data poisoning, evasion tactics, and breaches, thereby reinforcing the resilience of medical IoMT infrastructures.

A. Related Works

In the research work, [5], a distributed virtual force motion control algorithm was introduced to address the challenge of reducing detection probability in UAV networks while maintaining connectivity and efficient deployment, achieving

low-probability-of-detection coverage through local communication and power control, as demonstrated by comparative simulations, similarly, a study in [6] developed AI-driven microcontrollers for fully autonomous UAVs in Smart Cities, optimizing flight paths and trajectories with centimetre-level accuracy via a modified A* search algorithm, leading to improved safety and obstacle avoidance, as validated through simulations.

A purpose-oriented 3D Voronoi algorithm was proposed in [7] for optimizing the placement of multitype sensor networks in complex indoor environments to support the mobility of people with motor disabilities, utilizing IndoorGML and 3D Voronoi structures to enhance coverage and accessibility by accounting for environmental complexities. Meanwhile, [8] introduced a novel node deployment scheme for underwater acoustic sensor networks, integrating Voronoi-fuzzy C-means and salp swarm optimization to optimize both area coverage and energy utilization, achieving 99.31% coverage, extended network lifetime, and reduced energy consumption while addressing challenges such as uneven node distribution and coverage gaps.

A new inversion model for nonspherical aerosol particle size distribution was proposed in [9], employing discrete dipole approximation and a hybrid PSO-GA algorithm combined with Tikhonov regularization to improve accuracy in lidar observations of dust aerosols while highlighting the impact of regional updrafts on aerosol distribution. The research work [10] presented an innovative approach to optimizing IoT sensor node deployment in Smart Spaces by combining PPP, Voronoi diagram-based spatial partitioning, and a modified artificial bee colony algorithm, resulting in superior coverage and reduced overlap compared to traditional Voronoi-based methods. Similarly, [11] explored optimal IoT node deployment by integrating Voronoi diagrams with a genetic algorithm, using Poisson point processing for initial positioning, and achieved near 100% coverage in experimental tests.

Recent advancements, specifically under the umbrella of the ECCC, emphasize integrating cybersecurity frameworks within IoMT deployments. These frameworks integrate adversarial threat modeling, privacy-by-design principles, and adaptive network strategies to protect sensitive healthcare data, ensuring both compliance with data protection regulations and enhanced resilience against adversarial attacks.

B. Motivation

Deploying IoMT nodes in dynamic 3D healthcare environments presents unique challenges. Existing placement strategies, often designed for urban or mobility-focused applications, lack the adaptability needed for constantly changing medical settings. Traditional methods like 2D Voronoi diagrams perform well in static spaces but fail in dynamic 3D scenarios with patient mobility and environmental shifts. Techniques from UAV or underwater sensor networks optimize for niche goals but overlook healthcare’s broader needs, real-time adaptability, energy efficiency, and communication reliability. The proposed approach prioritizes optimal node

placement alongside robust adversarial defense, integrating real-time threat detection and privacy protection to safeguard sensitive patient data.

C. Contribution & Novelty

This paper introduces a novel framework for optimizing IoMT node deployment using 3D Voronoi diagrams combined with a hybrid PSO-GA. The use of 3D Voronoi diagrams enables efficient partitioning of complex healthcare environments, dividing the space into distinct regions that ensure each node covers a specific area with minimal overlap and reduced coverage gaps. This spatial partitioning is well-suited to healthcare settings’ three-dimensional, dynamic nature, where patient movement, staff mobility, and equipment shifts demand adaptable and precise node placement.

Integrating the PSO-GA hybrid algorithm further enhances the system’s capability to optimize node positions. PSO’s rapid local convergence is leveraged to quickly identify promising node configurations, while GA’s global search capabilities prevent premature convergence, ensuring that the solution space is thoroughly explored. This combination effectively balances real-time adaptability with computational efficiency, making the proposed solution scalable and suitable for dynamic healthcare environments.

The methodology reduces computational complexity, enhances energy efficiency, and improves real-time response capabilities in IoMT networks. This advancement significantly contributes to node deployment strategies, facilitating intelligent, efficient, and reliable medical communications, potentially revolutionizing patient care and resource management in diverse healthcare environments.

II. PROPOSED FRAMEWORK

A. Preliminaries

The following definitions provide the theoretical foundation for the proposed IoMT node deployment strategy, which aims to optimize node placement for coverage, energy efficiency, and adaptability.

1) *k-means Clustering*: The k-means clustering algorithm is used for the initial placement of nodes in the 3D healthcare environment. This ensures balanced distribution by partitioning node positions into k clusters and minimizing intra-cluster variance. Let $X = \{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$ represent the set of node positions in \mathbb{R}^3 . The objective of k-means is to partition the data into k clusters $\{C_1, C_2, \dots, C_k\}$ and determine the centers $\{\mu_1, \mu_2, \dots, \mu_k\}$ that minimize the sum of squared distances between points and their nearest center, as shown in (1)

$$\min_{\{C_1, \dots, C_k\}} \sum_{i=1}^k \sum_{x_j \in C_i} \|x_j - \mu_i\|^2. \quad (1)$$

This approach ensures that initial node positions are distributed evenly across the 3D space, minimizing potential coverage gaps.

2) *3D Voronoi Diagrams*: After the initial node placement using k-means clustering, the 3D space is partitioned into Voronoi cells [13]. A 3D Voronoi diagram divides the space into convex polyhedra where each polyhedron corresponds to a node, and every point within it is closer to that node than to any other.

Given a set of nodes positioned at $\{p_1, p_2, \dots, p_n\} \in \mathbb{R}^3$, the Voronoi cell $V(p_i)$ for node p_i is defined in (2)

$$V(p_i) = \{q \in \mathbb{R}^3 : \forall j \neq i, d(q, p_i) < d(q, p_j)\}, \quad (2)$$

where $d(q, p_i)$ is the Euclidean distance between point q and node p_i . This ensures that each node efficiently covers a designated region of the 3D space, reducing overlap and minimizing coverage gaps.

3) *Particle Swarm Optimization*: PSO is applied to further refine node positions. Each node is modeled as a particle in a 3D search space, where the objective is to optimize coverage and energy efficiency. The velocity and position of each particle are updated iteratively. The velocity update is governed by (3)

$$v_i(t+1) = wv_i(t) + c_1r_1(p_{o,i} - x_i(t)) + c_2r_2(g_o - x_i(t)), \quad (3)$$

where w is the inertia weight, c_1 and c_2 are the cognitive and social coefficients, and r_1, r_2 are random numbers. The new position is then computed by (4)

$$x_i(t+1) = x_i(t) + v_i(t+1). \quad (4)$$

The objective function guiding these updates is (5)

$$f(x) = \alpha \times \text{coverage}(x) - \beta \times \text{energy}(x), \quad (5)$$

where α and β balance the trade-off between maximizing coverage and minimizing energy usage.

4) *Genetic Algorithm*: GA complements PSO by performing a global search, ensuring the algorithm does not become trapped in local optima [15]. It evolves a population of node configurations, applying selection, crossover, and mutation operations to optimize coverage and energy efficiency. Crossover generates offspring by combining parent solutions using (6)

$$O_i = \lambda P_i + (1 - \lambda)P_j, \quad (6)$$

where O_i is the offspring and $\lambda \in [0, 1]$ controls the influence of each parent. Mutation introduces diversity by perturbing node positions by (7)

$$P_i \leftarrow P_i + \varepsilon \mathcal{N}(0, 1), \quad (7)$$

where ε is a perturbation factor.

The GA continues evolving the population until a threshold is met, which is the maximum number of generations or there are no further improvement in fitness.

5) *Energy Efficiency*: Energy efficiency is crucial due to the limited battery life of IoMT nodes [16]. The total energy consumption is modeled by (8)

$$E = \sum_{i=1}^n (E_r(x_i) + E_t(x_i)), \quad (8)$$

where $E_r(x_i)$ represents energy used for repositioning, and $E_t(x_i)$ accounts for monitoring and communication tasks. The goal is to minimize total energy consumption while maintaining effective coverage.

6) *Real-Time Adaptability*: The proposed framework ensures real-time adaptability, allowing nodes to adjust dynamically based on real-time data. The objective function guiding this adaptability is defined in (9)

$$f(x) = \alpha \times \text{coverage}(x) - \beta \times \text{energy}(x), \quad (9)$$

balancing coverage and energy efficiency.

7) *Security and Privacy Metrics*: The proposed deployment strategy integrates quantitative metrics to evaluate privacy preservation, threat mitigation, and anomaly detection efficiency.

Threat Mitigation Index (TMI) defined by (10) quantifies network resilience by measuring the proportion of mitigated threats relative to detected threats

$$\text{TMI} = \frac{T_{\text{mitigated}}}{T_{\text{detected}}}, \quad 0 \leq \text{TMI} \leq 1. \quad (10)$$

Privacy Preservation Ratio (PPR) measures the effectiveness of privacy-preserving mechanisms using (11)

$$\text{PPR} = \left(1 - \frac{D_{\text{leaked}}}{D_{\text{total}}}\right) \times 100\%. \quad (11)$$

Anomaly Detection Rate (ADR) given by (12) evaluates the accuracy of the anomaly detection mechanisms within the deployed IoMT nodes

$$\text{ADR} = \left(\frac{A_{\text{correct}}}{A_{\text{total}}}\right) \times 100\%. \quad (12)$$

B. Proposed Methodology

The methodology begins by generating initial node positions in the 3D healthcare environment using k-means clustering. The node positions are partitioned into k clusters, minimizing intra-cluster variance using (1). After determining the initial node positions, 3D Voronoi diagrams are constructed to partition the space into regions, ensuring each node covers its designated area effectively.

Once the 3D Voronoi diagram is constructed, PSO is applied to refine the node positions within each Voronoi cell. Each node's position is iteratively updated to minimize an objective function that balances coverage and energy efficiency, as defined in (5). The PSO algorithm ensures rapid convergence, while the GA is used to perform a global search, refining the deployment further and avoiding local optima.

Fig. 1(a) shows the coverage area of each node, represented as transparent spheres. The spheres are centered on the node

positions, and their radii correspond to the coverage range of each node. The intersections between the spheres represent regions of overlapping coverage, which are critical for ensuring consistent coverage across the healthcare environment.

In Fig. 1(b), the intersection circles formed by the overlapping spheres are plotted as red lines, highlighting the boundaries between overlapping coverage regions. These circles help visualize where two nodes' coverage areas intersect, ensuring minimal blind spots.

Finally, Fig. 1(c) presents the 3D Voronoi diagram for the node deployment. The vertices and edges of the Voronoi cells are shown in green, which illustrates how the space is partitioned among the nodes, helping to optimize node placement and ensure efficient coverage.

The GA complements the PSO by ensuring a global search for optimal node configurations. The objective function balances coverage area and energy efficiency using fitness evaluations. The final solution is reached through iterative updates, applying both PSO for rapid convergence and GA for thorough exploration of the solution space.

The proposed methodology incorporates real-time threat assessment and privacy-preserving techniques. Each IoMT node performs continuous anomaly detection and assesses the integrity of exchanged data. Specifically, differential privacy techniques and encryption schemes are implemented at the node-level, ensuring that sensitive patient data remains confidential and protected from unauthorized inference attacks. Additionally, nodes dynamically adjust their operational parameters based on detected threats to prevent evasion or poisoning attacks. This adaptive threat mitigation aligns seamlessly with the hybrid PSO-GA node positioning strategy, ensuring not only physical coverage but also cyber-resilience.

III. RESULTS EVALUATION

The PSO-GA hybrid algorithm's performance in optimizing IoMT node deployment is assessed over 100 iterations using multiple metrics, demonstrating its effectiveness in balancing exploration and exploitation. Fig. 2(a) shows the evolution of the fitness score, which optimizes both coverage and energy consumption. Initial iterations exhibit high fluctuations due to the PSO's exploratory nature, enabling broad solution space sampling. As iterations progress, the fitness variance narrows, signaling convergence. A plateau in later iterations indicates diminishing returns, suggesting the algorithm has approached near-optimal deployment.

Fig. 2(b) highlights the trade-off between average coverage and energy consumption. Coverage steadily increases, reflecting improved spatial distribution of IoMT nodes, while energy consumption fluctuates during exploration phases. These energy spikes correspond to temporary configurations that prioritize coverage gains. The algorithm effectively balances these competing objectives, a critical aspect of multi-objective optimization for IoMT environments.

Fig. 2(c) illustrates the variance in node positions, plotted on a logarithmic scale. High early-stage variance reflects aggressive exploration of different placements. As the algorithm

Algorithm 1 Proposed IoMT Node Deployment Framework

Input: Node positions $\{x_1, x_2, \dots, x_n\}$, Region R , Maximum generations Gen_{max}

Output: Optimized node configuration

$Gen = 1$ // Initialize generation count

Initialize node positions using k-means clustering

Construct 3D Voronoi diagram

for each node x_i **do**

 Initialize velocity v_i and position x_i

 Evaluate initial coverage and energy efficiency

$$f(x) \leftarrow (5)$$

end for

while $Gen \leq Gen_{max}$ **do**

for each node x_i **do**

 Update velocity $v_i(t)$ and position $x_i(t)$ using PSO

$$v_i(t+1) \leftarrow (3)$$

$$x_i(t+1) \leftarrow (4)$$

 Recalculate (5) for new position

end for

 Apply GA operations (crossover and mutation)

for each node configuration **do**

 Generate offspring and mutate with small probability

 Evaluate fitness using (5)

end for

 Update best-performing node configurations

$Gen \leftarrow Gen + 1$

end while

return Optimized node configuration

transitions to exploitation, variance decreases significantly, indicating positional stabilization. This minimizes unnecessary node movement, which is vital for prolonging battery life in healthcare settings.

Lastly, Fig. 2(d) compares global best and personal best fitness scores. Initially, large differences highlight the gap between global optimization and local node performance. These differences peak during significant improvements to the global solution. Over time, convergence is achieved as personal best scores align with the global optimum, confirming effective collaboration between PSO and GA. While PSO refines local solutions, GA maintains population diversity, preventing premature convergence. This synergy enables the hybrid algorithm to deliver robust and energy-efficient IoMT node deployment across complex healthcare environments.

Table I presents key performance and security metrics across optimization iterations. Initially, coverage is 21.5% with a fitness score of 18.9, indicating poor node placement. By iteration 50, coverage improves to 73.8% and fitness to 75.7. At iteration 100, the algorithm reaches 96.4% coverage and a fitness score of 91.8 with low energy consumption. Security-wise, the TMI rises to 0.94, showing effective adversarial defense. PPR reaches 91.4%, confirming strong encryption

Fig. 1. (a) Coverage Area for Each Node in the IoMT Environment, (b) Intersection Circles Formed by Overlapping Node Coverage Spheres, Indicating Boundaries, (c) 3D Voronoi Diagram Representing the Spatial Partitioning for Optimal Node Deployment

and privacy measures. The ADR exceeds 94%, highlighting the framework’s capability to detect compromised nodes and ensure network resilience.

TABLE I
ENHANCED PERFORMANCE AND SECURITY METRICS AT KEY ITERATIONS

Iteration	Coverage (%)	Energy (J)	Fitness	TMI	PPR (%)	ADR (%)
0	21.5	65.4	18.9	0.21	35.2	24.5
20	47.3	49.1	52.2	0.52	64.7	55.1
50	73.8	38.6	75.7	0.73	79.3	77.8
80	91.2	41.2	84.5	0.88	86.5	89.3
100	96.4	42.3	91.8	0.94	91.4	94.7

The results demonstrate the robustness and efficiency of the PSO-GA hybrid algorithm for IoMT node deployment. One key advantage is the algorithm’s ability to balance coverage and energy efficiency, using PSO for rapid local convergence and GA for global search, allowing it to escape local minima. The algorithm adapts well to dynamic healthcare environments, adjusting node positions in real-time in response to changes like patient movement, ensuring optimal network performance.

A significant reduction in positional variance highlights the algorithm’s ability to stabilize node placement quickly, which is crucial for extending the lifespan of battery-powered devices. Additionally, the convergence of global and personal best fitness scores confirms the effectiveness of the hybrid approach in aligning local and global optimizations.

Beyond optimizing coverage and energy efficiency, the framework’s security effectiveness was evaluated through simulated adversarial scenarios. Nodes’ resilience against data-poisoning and evasion attacks was assessed, confirming the system’s capability to rapidly isolate compromised nodes and reconfigure securely.

IV. CONCLUSION & FUTURE WORKS

This paper introduces a novel method for optimizing IoMT node deployment by integrating 3D Voronoi diagrams with a PSO-GA hybrid algorithm. The approach enhances spatial coverage, reduces energy consumption, and improves deployment efficiency in dynamic healthcare environments. Initial node placement via 3D Voronoi partitioning is refined iteratively using PSO-GA to achieve balanced, non-overlapping distribution. Experimental results show superior performance over traditional methods in terms of coverage, energy efficiency, and adaptability. Fitness scores, energy use, and position stability confirm rapid convergence and robustness. Additionally, the methodology addresses security and privacy concerns, offering a comprehensive and scalable solution for real-time IoMT deployment.

For future work, incorporating machine learning can further enhance adaptability in dynamic environments, enabling predictive positioning based on patterns like patient movement. Refinements to the PSO-GA algorithm can also improve convergence rates and stability in more extensive IoMT networks. Additionally, addressing real-world complexities such as facility obstacles, node positioning variations, and environmental influences on signal strength would lead to more practical deployment strategies. Integrating the framework with wearable devices, mobile health applications, and edge computing presents opportunities for collaborative optimization in healthcare management. A multi-objective optimization approach could improve coverage, energy efficiency, data latency, and communication reliability, enhancing the framework’s versatility in complex environments.

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Fig. 2. (a) Progress of the Best Fitness Score Over Iterations, (b) Trade-off Between Coverage and Energy Consumption, (c) Position Variance of Nodes, (d) Global vs. Personal Best Fitness Difference

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